

Kinetics of hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid in acetone-water medium

Nitin Choure, P. Awadhiya and S. A. Bhoite*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010, Chhattisgarh, India

E-mail : nitin.choure1@gmail.com; sa.bhoite10@gmail.com

Manuscript received 24 April 2009, accepted 18 May 2009

Abstract : The kinetics of hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid have been studied in 1.8 to 8.1 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ at 55 °C. The rate of reaction increases with increasing concentration of H₂SO₄, nearly linearly up to 7.2 mol dm⁻³ and then increased sharply. The rate maximum was not observed. The effect of temperature on the rate of hydrolysis has been studied. Activation parameters have been calculated. Bimolecular nature of hydrolysis has been supported by Arrhenius parameters, Bunnett-Olsen, Zucker-Hammett hypothesis etc.

Keywords : Kinetic, hydrolysis, *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid.

Introduction

Hydroxamate ions are α -effect nucleophiles whose reactivities are higher than that predicted by relationship between nucleophilicity and basicity¹⁻³. Hydroxamic acids have been found to react with both proteins and nucleic acid⁴ and their derivatives fulfill a variety of important role in analytical, biological and medicinal fields such as drug delivery system, iron-transport and DNA cleavage etc. Hydroxamic acids when paired with carbonyl and hydroxylamine (-NOH), the functional groups acquired phenomenal importance because of their tremendous applications in all spheres of life. They are iron chelators with therapeutic potential⁵ and also specific enzyme inhibitors⁶. Hydroxamic acid based metal chelation⁷ therapy is useful for the treatment of HIV, Alzheimers disease⁸, cancer⁹ and tuberculosis¹⁰. Hydroxamic acid containing polymer points are used as corrosion inhibitors¹¹, the treatment of transition metals containing pigment particles¹², laundry detergents and as surfactants¹³.

Experimental

N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) was prepared as described earlier^{14,15}. Its purity was tested by melting point and also by IR spectral analysis. Standardization of acid was done by standard alkali solution. The ferric chloride solution used in colorimetric procedure was prepared by dissolving 44.0 g of anhydrous ferric chloride in one litre distilled water containing 10.0 ml of concentrated HCl. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

All kinetic measurements were carried out at 45 °C and 55 °C respectively. The concentration of PBHA was monitored spectrophotometrically¹⁶ employing a Spekol instrument at 520 nm. The reaction of Fe³⁺ with hydroxamic acid yields a violet coloured complex

$$[\text{Fe}(\overset{\text{R}}{\text{CON-OH}})^2]^+$$
 exhibiting stability at pH ~ 1.0. Pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated.

Results and discussion

Hydrolysis of PBHA has been kinetically investigated in (1.8 to 8.1 mol dm⁻³) H₂SO₄ at 55 °C. The rate of reaction first increases with increasing concentration of H₂SO₄, almost linearly up to 7.2 mol dm⁻³ and then increase sharply at (H⁺) > 7.2 mol dm⁻³. The rate maximum was not observed. Pseudo-first order rate constants determined by first order equation have been summarized in Table 1. The rate increases with hydrogen ion concentration. The ionized form of hydroxamic acid is responsible for the increase in rate constant. The hydrolysis proceeds via conjugate acid species with N-C=O bond fission¹⁷.

Molecularity of a solvolytic reaction has been determined using Zucker-Hammett hypothesis¹⁸. The hypothesis consists of two parts. The first part deals with acidity function¹⁹ (H₀) and the slope of the plot (Fig. 1) has been taken to account for nature of the reaction. The second part of the hypothesis deals with the plot between

Table 1. Rate constants for the hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic (PBHA) acid

Temp. = 55 °C, k_e = experimental rate

H_2SO_4 (mol dm^{-3})	k_e (min^{-1})	$4 + \log k_e$
1.80	3.63	0.56
2.70	5.02	0.70
3.60	6.87	0.84
4.50	8.13	0.91
5.40	9.07	0.96
5.85	9.27	0.97
6.30	10.22	1.01
7.20	11.92	1.08
7.65	16.94	1.23
8.10	29.27	1.47

Table 2. Hammett and Zucker-Hammett rate data for the hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid

H_2SO_4 (mol dm^{-3})	$\log c_{H^+}$	$-H_0$	k_e (min^{-1})	$4 + \log k_e$
1.80	0.26	0.68	3.63	0.56
2.70	0.43	1.14	5.02	0.70
3.60	0.56	1.62	6.87	0.84
4.50	0.65	2.08	8.13	0.91
5.40	0.73	2.50	9.07	0.96
5.85	0.77	2.74	9.27	0.97
6.30	0.80	3.00	10.22	1.01
7.20	0.86	3.44	11.92	1.08
7.65	0.88	3.65	16.94	1.23
8.10	0.91	3.90	29.27	1.47

Fig 1. Hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA).

Fig. 2. Hammett plot for the hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid.

log-rate constant and log of acid molarity. Unit or the unit slope of such a curve is presumed to indicate the nature of reaction. The relevant data for Hammett and Zucker-Hammett hypothesis have been summarized in Table 2.

The magnitude of the Arrhenius parameters falls in the range of bimolecular reaction. Bimolecular nature of reaction is further supported by plots of Hammett (Fig. 2) (slope value 0.22), Zucker-Hammett (Fig. not shown) (slope value 0.84).

Bunnett²⁰ suggested different plots (log rate constant + H_0) and (log rate constant $-\log c_{H^+}$) were separately plotted against log activity of water ($-\log a_{H_2O}$) and their

slopes were respectively denoted by parameters ω and ω^* . In present case of PBHA, the slope value (ω) is 8.40 which indicate the reaction is bimolecular in nature. The slope (ω^*) is another parameter which is obtained from the plot of $\log k_e - \log c_{H^+}$ and $-\log a_{H_2O}$. The value is equal to -0.32 . Bunnett-Olsen suggested a new parameter i.e. ϕ which is a slope of plot between $\log k_e + H_0$ and $-\log c_{H^+} + H_0$. The value of the slope -1.04 which is in favour of the fact that water activity is playing an important role in deciding the rate at higher acidic concentration and water is involved in slow step. Activation parameters for the *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid were

Table 3. Thermodynamic activation parameters of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid in acetone-water media

H_2SO_4	E_a	$\log A$		ΔS		ΔH		ΔG		Temp. coeff.
		45 °C	55 °C	45 °C	55 °C	45 °C	55 °C	45 °C	55 °C	
6.3	23.8	12.1	12.1	-3.5	-3.5	23.1	23.1	24.2	24.3	3.15
7.2	20.2	9.7	9.7	-14.1	-14.2	19.5	19.5	24.0	24.2	2.64
7.65	22.7	11.6	11.6	-5.7	-5.7	22.1	22.1	23.9	23.9	3.00
8.1	24.6	13.1	13.1	+1.1	+1.0	23.9	23.6	23.6	23.6	3.27

determined by measuring the rate of hydrolysis at 45 °C and 55 °C respectively and these parameters such as E_a , ΔH , ΔS and ΔG are shown in Table 3 which clearly confirms the nature of the reaction to be bimolecular.

Conclusion :

Hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) has been found via conjugate acid species with N=C=O bond fission. Bimolecular nature of hydrolysis has been supported by different parameters such as Hammett, Zucker-Hammett, Bunnett, Bunnett-Olsen and Arrhenius etc.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur for providing research facilities.

References

1. C. A. Bunton, A. Blasko, N. D. Gillitt and H. J. Foroudian, *Langmuir*, 1998, **14**, 4415.
2. K. R. Fountaun, C. J. Felkerson, J. D. Driskell and B. D. Lamp, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2003, **68**, 1810.
3. K. R. Fountain, D. B. Tady, T. W. Paul and M. V. Golynskiy, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **58**, 7883.
4. H. M. Niemeyer, E. Pesel, S. V. Copaja, H. R. Bravo and S. Franke, *Photochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 47.
5. M. J. Miller, *J. Chem. Rev.*, 1989, **89**, 1563.
6. A. O. Stewart and J. G. Martin, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1989, **54**, 1221.
7. A. L. Crumbliss, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **55**, 105.
8. J. E. Yajal and Y. P. Pang, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 2000, **104**, 6499.
9. R. Brammer, J. Buckels and S. Bramhall, *Int. J. Clin. Pract.*, 2000, **54**, 373.
10. M. J. Miller, *J. Chem. Rev.*, 1989, **89**, 1563.
11. D. W. Fong and B. F. Khambatta, Eurpat, Ep. (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2000, **4**, 119, 29286j).
12. W. Kwan and V. Sum, PCT. Int. Appl. 9712, 944 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1997, **126**, 24, 378493y).
13. E. A. Kaezkar, C. O. Gitterman, E. L. Dulaney and K. K. Falkers, *Biochemistry*, 1962, **1**, 340.
14. C. A. Bunton, J. H. Crabtree and Robinson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 1258.
15. Usha Priyadar Shing and S. G. Tandon, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1967, **12**, 143.
16. Subba Rao and S. G. Tandon, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1972, **35**, 23.
17. K. K. Ghosh, Jyoti Vaidya and Manmohan Lal Satnami, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2006, **38**, 26.
18. F. A. Long and M. A. Paul, *Chem. Rev.*, 1957, **57**, 2.
19. L. P. Hammett, "Physical Organic Chemistry", McGraw Hill Book Company, London, 1940, 273.
20. J. F. Bunnett and F. F. Olsen, *Canadian J. Chem.*, 1966, **44**, 1917.